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4 **USING DUCTILE CORES FOR ENHANCING THE MECHANICAL**
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7 **PERFORMANCE OF HOLLOW STRUT β -TCP SCAFFOLDS**
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10 **FABRICATED BY DIGITAL LIGHT PROCESSING**
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4 **Abstract**
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6 Hybrid scaffolds consisting of a three-dimensional network of hollow struts of β -tricalcium
7 phosphate (β -TCP) with cores filled with polycaprolactone (PCL) were fabricated. For the
8 development of the ceramic structures the additive manufacturing technique known as
9 Digital Light Processing (DLP) was employed. After sintering, cores were infiltrated with
10 molten PCL by suction. The enhancement of the scaffolds' compressive strength and
11 toughness upon infiltration was evaluated through uniaxial compression tests. The effect of
12 the core diameter on the mechanical performance was also analyzed. Moreover, a
13 comprehensive finite element analysis was carried out to broaden the study on the effect of
14 core/shell respective diameters and to analyze the role of the modulus of the core material on
15 the strength of the hybrid structure.
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33 **Keywords:** composite scaffolds; ceramic; polymer; mechanical properties; digital light
34 processing, finite element method.
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1. Introduction

The use of artificial implants to restore the function of a damaged part of the skeleton is increasingly frequent as a consequence, among other causes, of the progressive population's ageing. Hence, the development of novel biomaterials with mechanical and biological performances more similar to natural bone tissues than currently available alternatives is paramount. This would allow to solve, or at least mitigate, the current problems associated to the use of prostheses or implants made from inert materials, like bone resorption and the subsequent need of replacement surgeries [1,2].

When bone regeneration instead of just damage repair is the goal, the only choice is to use bioactive scaffolds: porous structures fabricated from materials that can interact with the surrounding tissues [2,3]. This is the case of polymers that in contact to organic fluids are degraded [4] or bioactive ceramics that can also actively induce cell anchorage and proliferation [5–8], disappearing completely from the organism once the defect has been healed. The main hurdle to the widespread use of these materials lies in their mechanical properties: biopolymers are mechanically weak [7,9] and ceramics extremely brittle [9,10], and thus they typically require the joint use of temporary metallic plates to provide the necessary mechanical support during bone healings. Moreover, the mechanical performance of these already weak materials is further compromised when they are used to fabricate the porous structure of scaffolds using traditional manufacturing techniques.

The combined use of both types of materials, bioceramics and biopolymers, together with the use of additive manufacturing techniques for scaffold fabrication are emerging strategies that several authors are using to overcome these problems. It is, thus, possible to fabricate a ceramic matrix with a controlled porosity either coated or fully impregnated by a polymeric phase [11–16], which provides toughness to the ceramic skeleton, achieving very promising

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4 results in terms of mechanical performance. A schematic of both approaches is shown in
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6 Figure 1a.

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9 The biological performance of the scaffolds depends on their microstructure (surface
10 roughness, edges sharpness, pore size and interconnectivity, etc.) [1,17] as well as on their
11 surface composition. Direct exposure of the bioactive ceramic phase to the surrounding
12 tissue typically implies a more effective osteoconduction [18] and faster biodegradation [19].
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14 Therefore, one way of achieving hybrid scaffolds with preserved osteoconductivity is to use
15 a coaxial architecture comprised of struts with polymeric cores and ceramic outer shells
16 (Figure1b). Various authors have already successfully fabricated ceramic-scaffolds with
17 hollow struts by means of the additive manufacturing technique, often referred to as direct
18 ink writing (DIW) or robocasting, using coaxial nozzles [20–23]. Once sintered, it was
19 demonstrated that it is possible to infiltrate the internal channels of the ceramic struts with a
20 biodegradable polymer, either using polymeric solutions, in-situ polymerization or polymer
21 melts. Thus, it is possible to obtain substantial mechanical improvements in terms of
22 toughness, especially with the last option, as it allows for a complete impregnation of the
23 channels with the polymeric phase.
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28 In this work, hollow-strut scaffolds were fabricated via Digital Light Processing (DLP), an
29 additive manufacturing technique which has nominally better resolution than robocasting
30 and, thus, has greater potential for the fabrication of finer ceramic structures with more
31 complex geometry by incorporating ceramic fillers into the photosensitive resins [24–28].
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33 Indeed, DLP should be able to produce hollow-strut scaffolds with better external shape and
34 surface finish, and an internal channel geometry exhibiting less distortions and defects than
35 those which are typically found in this type of structures when they are fabricated by coaxial
36 extrusion (i.e. by DIW) due to the complexity of the process. A subsequent heat treatment is
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4 used to remove the photocurable resin and finally obtain sintered all-ceramic structures.
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6 However, the addition of particles to the resin negatively affects the behavior of the resin in
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8 two ways: first, by producing light scattering due to the refractive index mismatch between
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10 the two components in the suspension [24,29,30], and secondly by increasing its viscosity.
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12 Light scattering reduces the effective resolution of the process and the increase in viscosity
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14 compromises the correct flow of material during printing [24,29] and the conversion reaction
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16 [30]. Ideal viscosities must not exceed 3000 mPa·s, in order to allow for a correct flow of the
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18 resin [29].
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23 As well as providing an evaluation of the DLP fabrication technique for the production of
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25 hollow-strut scaffolds and the subsequent fabrication of hybrid core/shell structures, the
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27 mechanical behavior of this type of structures was thoroughly analyzed in this work. The
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29 contribution of the polymeric cores in terms of strength and toughness was evaluated under
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31 compression stresses in hybrid scaffolds with two different core diameters. This experimental
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33 study was also broadened by a numerical finite element analysis of the effect of core/shell
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35 diameter and modulus ratios on the strength and stiffness of these hybrid scaffolds.
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43 **2. Materials and methods**

44 **2.1. Scaffold fabrication**

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46 DLP printing parameters as determined in a previous investigation [31] were used for the
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48 fabrication of the hollow bioceramic scaffolds: suspensions with 50 wt.% of β -TCP powder
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50 content (particle size 2.36 μm , density 3.07 g/cm^3 and refractive index 1.63) in a commercial
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52 unpigmented acrylic resin (FTD Standard Blend 3D Printing resin, Fun to Do, Alkmaar, The
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54 Netherland, with a density of 1.13 g/cm^3 and refractive index of 1.5) were used as feedstock.
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56 To control the cure depth, 0.75 wt.% of pigment was added as photo-absorber. All elements
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4 were mixed in a centrifugal planetary mixer (ARE-250 Thinky Corp., Tokyo, Japan) in
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6 intervals of 5 min at 2000 r.p.m., and then the mix was kept under magnetic stirring
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8 overnight at 50 °C to ensure its homogeneity.
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11 Before fabrication, scaffolds containing 7 layers of either hollow or dense rods arranged
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13 perpendicularly to each other were designed (Figure 2). For the hybrid structures,
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15 appendages and outer channels were added to the design to enable PCL impregnation. The
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17 external dimensions of those scaffolds were 7×7×8 mm. After heat treatment, just the
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19 appendages and external channels for infiltration were cut, resulting in similar final
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21 dimensions to those of dense- and hollow-strut scaffolds: 5×5×6 mm. These dimensions were
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23 chosen to be similar to those used in previous works. This design was chosen to simulate
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25 structures that can be printed using the DIW technique. The centre-to-centre distance
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27 between struts within the same layer or *spacing* (s), was set to be twice the rod external
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29 diameter (d) = 1.57 mm, and the spacing between consecutive layers or *layer height* (h) was
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31 set at 0.8 d , to produce an overlapping of 20% between the stacked rods to facilitate
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33 adhesion. Structures with hollow struts were created with two different *internal diameters*
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35 (d_i) for the tubular struts. Thus, scaffolds with d_i/d ratios of 0.45 and 0.60 were designed,
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37 with the intention of evaluating the impact on strength and toughness of the size of the
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39 polymeric cores after infiltration of the hollow structures. Hollow structures were designed
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41 including also additional feeding channels, aimed at facilitating the infiltration of the
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43 polymer into the channels. STL-files of the digital models were exported to the DLP-system
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45 software 3DLPrinter-HD 2.0 (Robotfactory, Venice, Italy) for subsequent slicing and
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47 printing, using a layer thickness (l_i) of 25 µm.
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51 For printing, the TCP-resin suspension was poured into a transparent vat and placed in the
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53 DLP printer, where images corresponding to each of the scaffold slices were projected using
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4 UV-light of a wavelength in the range of 400-500 nm. Thus, the polymerization of the resin
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6 is induced trapping the ceramic particles in place. Printed parts remain attached to a
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8 suspended platform over the vat as the printing progresses layer by layer in the selected
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10 bottom-up DLP system (Figure 3). After printing, the parts were immersed in isopropanol
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12 within an ultrasonic bath, and then blown with compressed air to remove any traces of
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14 uncured slurry. Cleaned parts were then post-cured in a UV-light chamber and subsequently
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16 heat treated in a controlled atmosphere tubular furnace.
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21 To avoid cracking during the heat-treatment, a problem especially critical in the case of large
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23 structures with thick walls, de-binding was performed in nitrogen atmosphere [32,33] at a
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25 very slow heating rate, 0.3 °C/min, up to 450 °C, holding that temperature for 5 hours to
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27 ensure the complete elimination of the acrylic resin in a controlled way. Once the ceramic is
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29 free of resin, a heating rate of 3 °C/min was set up to a temperature of 1200 °C for its
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31 sintering for 2 hours.
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35 Polycaprolactone (Capa 6500, Perstorp Holding AB, $M_w = 50\ 000$) was the biodegradable
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37 polymer selected to fill the internal channels of the hollow struts. To this end, PCL was
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39 heated to 180 °C in a hot plate and one of the samples' feeding channels was immersed in the
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41 molten polymer while vacuum was applied at the opposite end. **No pre-heating was applied**
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43 **to the scaffold to facilitate handling.** Figure 3 shows the infiltration process and the paths the
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45 polymer follows through the channels. After the infiltration process, the feeding channels and
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47 external walls were cut out and scaffolds with the same dimensions than those of the dense
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49 and hollow specimens were obtained for following characterization.
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57 **2.2. Microstructural characterization**

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4 The microstructure of the fabricated scaffolds was analyzed by scanning electron microscopy
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6 (SEM). The mean dimensions of the structures were evaluated from SEM images for all type
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8 of fabricated specimens, before and after sintering.
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10 11 12 13 14 **2.3. Mechanical characterization**

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16 Average compressive strength values (σ_c) and their corresponding standard deviations were
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18 estimated for each type of sample from the specimens' external dimensions and their
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20 corresponding peak value in the load-displacement data obtained in uniaxial compression
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22 tests. Tests were performed in air by applying the load perpendicularly to the printing plane
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24 at a constant crosshead speed of 0.6 mm/min on a universal testing machine (AG-IS10kN,
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26 Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). A minimum of 7 specimens with external dimensions around 5×5
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28 $\times 6 \text{ mm}^3$ were used for each type of specimens. To evaluate the improvement in toughness
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30 obtained upon infiltration, average strain energy densities of each type of sample were
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32 evaluated from the area under the nominal stress-strain curves up to a strain of 0.4 ($G_{0.4}$).
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38 Instrumented indentation (Nanotest, Micro Materials, Wrexham, UK) was used to determine
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40 the elastic modulus of the individual materials in the scaffolds, which was then used as input
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42 parameter for some numerical simulations.
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48 **2.4. Numerical modeling**

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50 Models of scaffolds with infiltrated struts were employed to perform finite elements
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52 simulations in ABAQUS/Standard software (Dassault Systemes Simulia Corp., France), in
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54 order to analyze the stress fields developed under compression tests. In these models, the
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56 ratio d_i/d was varied from 0.3 to 0.6 in 0.05 steps, while maintaining a constant external
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4 diameter; the selected range includes the two values corresponding to the fabricated
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6 scaffolds.

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9 External dimensions of the simulated scaffolds were 5.8 x 5.48 x 5.19 mm, and the struts
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11 dimensions were also similar to those measured for the real scaffolds: $d = 1.57$, $s = 2d$ and h
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13 $= 0.8d$. As for the fabricated scaffolds, the models used in the simulations consisted of 7
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15 alternating orthogonal layers. Top and bottom layers were cut in half to avoid unnecessary
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17 stress concentrations during numerical modelling upon loading along the top and bottom
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19 surfaces. The FEM grid for the scaffold system (Figure 4) consisted of tetrahedral quadratic
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21 elements with improved stress formulation (C3D10I). The model was partitioned to define a
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23 central cell, which is representative of the whole architecture of the scaffold to be meshed
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25 using finer elements ($\sim 25 \mu\text{m}$ at the scaffold surfaces, with moderate growth towards the
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27 struts interior) than the remaining regions (maximum size of $200 \mu\text{m}$). Thus, stress field
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29 resolution was maximized while keeping the computation time reasonable.

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36 As the ceramic failure is expected to occur at strains within the elastic regime, an isotropic
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38 elastic behavior was assumed for the entire hybrid system. **No attempt was made at**
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40 **simulating fracture initiation or propagation.** For the ceramic shell, elastic properties of
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42 βTCP ($\nu = 0.28$ [34], $E = 65 \text{ GPa}$) were used as input parameters. For the material in the
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44 core, and in order to evaluate its effect on the stress field developed in the ceramic scaffold,
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46 different elastic modulus values were used so that the elastic modulus ratio between the core
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48 and shell materials, E_{core}/E_{shell} , varied from ~ 0 (10^{-10}) to 1. In order to be able to compare the
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50 results of the simulation with the experimental data, an elastic modulus for the core of 0.47
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52 GPa, corresponding to that of the PCL polymer, was also used [35].

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58 Fixed boundary conditions were imposed at the bottom surface of the scaffold, while the top
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60 surface was displaced perpendicularly by $200 \mu\text{m}$, thus simulating a uniaxial compression

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4 test (Figure 4). The reaction force corresponding to such strain was calculated from the
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6 simulations and normalized by the initial surface area to obtain the nominal applied stress,
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9 σ_a .

10 11 12 13 14 **3. Results and discussion**

15 16 **3.1. Microstructural characterization**

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18 Representative SEM cross-sectional micrographs of sintered scaffolds with dense, hollow
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20 and hybrid ceramic/polymer struts are shown in Figure 5. The individual layers stacking
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22 along the printing direction (vertical on the image), is evident on the surface of the struts in
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24 these images, due to the typical “stair stepping” effect of DLP (layer height was set at 25
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26 μm). A good definition of the struts shapes is also evident, marred only by some localized
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28 surface defects, which was apparent already after the cleaning step. The adhesion between
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30 layers was very good in all areas, with no clear evidence of the existence of any interlayer
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32 defects.

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34 This can be more clearly seen in the cross-sectional micrographs of Figure 6: stair-steps for
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36 each layer are evident at the external surfaces (Fig.6a), but not on the polished strut sections
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38 (Fig.6c). Some residual microporosity is also apparent in these images, evidencing that
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40 densification during sintering is not complete, as is typically the case for β -TCP powders
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42 [36].

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44 The internal channels of the hollow specimens (Figs. 5d-f) showed the same superficial
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46 features as the external surfaces of the struts but appeared uniform and free of any
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48 photocurable resin residue within. Consequently, a complete infiltration of the channels with
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50 the molten PCL was possible (Figs. 5g-i). We can also observe that the channels within the
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52 hollow-strut scaffolds before or after impregnation with the polymer deviated slightly from
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4 the designed circular shape, which can be attributed to a slight deformation of the structure
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6 occurring during printing. Differences in the size of the channel are also apparent between
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8 the hollow (Figs. 5d-f) and hybrid (Figs. 5g-i) scaffolds, since the former corresponds to a
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10 model with $d_i/d = 0.6$ and the later to $d_i/d = 0.45$. Finally, the adhesion between the polymer
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12 and the ceramic **appears to be** very good, with no evidence of any gaps at the interface,
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14 although there is no **clear** sign of **significant** penetration of the polymer into the micropores
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16 of the ceramic shell **either**. Nonetheless, the polymer does seem to fill the core completely,
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18 without any sign of trapped bubbles within the solidified polymer, **and closely follows the**
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20 **roughness of the channel walls.**

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26 Density values were obtained from external dimensions of the specimen and their weight:
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28 dense struts scaffolds had an apparent density of $1.34 \pm 0.06 \text{ g/cm}^3$, hollow-strut scaffolds
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30 yielded $1.15 \pm 0.07 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $0.95 \pm 0.09 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for $d_i/d = 0.45$ and $d_i/d = 0.6$, respectively,
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33 and hybrid specimens $1.27 \pm 0.08 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $1.24 \pm 0.15 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Considering the theoretical
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35 density values of TCP, it was possible to estimate a total porosity of roughly 56 vol% for the
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37 dense scaffolds, and 63% and 69% for hollow scaffolds with $d_i/d = 0.45$ and $d_i/d = 0.6$,
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39 respectively. Taking into account these density measurements, and the theoretical density of
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41 PCL, it was possible to estimate that the hybrid structures with $d_i/d = 0.45$ and $d_i/d = 0.6$
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43 contained around 10 and 25 vol.% of PCL, respectively. This amount of polymer is located
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45 mainly within the central channels but, despite the lack of direct SEM confirmation, the
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47 impregnation of the micropores located at the internal surface of the ceramic shells is very
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49 likely, as the microporosity within the TCP shell was previously evaluated by mercury
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51 porosimetry to be ~26 vol.% [31]. In any case, the fact that suction impregnation was
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53 successful rules out the possibility of any through-thickness interconnected open porosity.
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4 Such porosity would have produced a loss of vacuum and prevented an effective suction of the
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6 polymer into the channels.
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9 The dimensions of the fabricated scaffolds were measured from the SEM images for all
10 specimen groups before and after sintering. The results are summarized in Figure 7, as mean
11 values with standard deviation as error, and compared to initial model dimensions. Green
12 bodies were slightly larger (by less than 4%) in all dimensions than the initial 3D-model. This
13 small difference could, in principle, be attributed to over-exposure and/or light scattering
14 caused by the ceramic powder, but the fact that the internal diameter is also larger than in the
15 model seems to contradict that explanation. Pixel size limitations of the UV projector could
16 also be responsible for the small discrepancies. In any case, the differences found are of the
17 same order as the scattering in the actual measurements, which all in all highlights the great
18 accuracy and reproducibility of the DLP AM technique.
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33 Linear shrinkage of the parts upon sintering is evident, amounting to approximately a 30%
34 contraction, and was found to be quite isotropic, indicating that the distribution of ceramic
35 powder within the volume of the struts was quite homogeneous due to the good stability of
36 the starting ceramic slurry.
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45 **3.2. Mechanical characterization**

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47 Representative stress-strain curves for all types of fabricated scaffolds under uniaxial
48 compressive stresses are shown in Figure 8. All-ceramic scaffolds, that is specimens with
49 dense and hollow struts, exhibited a typical brittle behavior. They suffered a catastrophic
50 failure, identified by the sudden load drop after the maximum in the curve is reached, while
51 still in the elastic regime. On the contrary both composite scaffolds showed sustained load-
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4 bearing capacity, even after large strains, thanks to the contribution of the PCL in the cores
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6 that held the structure together after the outer ceramic shell failed.
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9 On the other hand, the analysis of *in situ* images recorded during the compression tests
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11 revealed that fracture initiated, for all the cases, in regions close to the intersections between
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13 orthogonal rods (Figure 9, see arrows). More precisely, cracks in both all-ceramic and hybrid
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15 structures seem to propagate mainly in Mode I, driven by tensile stresses. However, there are
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17 a few experimental observations compatible with shear-induced fracture (Figure 9c). This is
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19 not dissimilar to what was observed in other scaffolds with fully interpenetrated dense
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21 squared struts fabricated with TCP by DLP in a previous work [31].
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25 In good agreement with the experimental observations, the finite element analysis of the
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27 stress fields (Figure 10) shows that, in all cases, the maximum stresses appear near the
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29 contact areas between struts. However, while the location of the tensile stress maxima, and
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31 thus the site for crack initiation, is found at the external surface of the ceramic struts in dense
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33 scaffolds (Fig. 10a), the maximum stresses move towards the internal channel in the hollow-
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35 strut and hybrid scaffolds (Fig. 10b-c). On the other hand, the infiltration of the channel with
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37 a polymer reduces slightly the intensity of the maximum stress values, as the polymer now
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39 can support part of the load. More importantly, however, the displacement of the maximum
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41 tensile stresses to the interior of the channels indicates that the addition of the polymeric
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43 phase may result beneficial also in sealing fracture precursor flaws at those locations. Such
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45 defect healing is typically found to be more effective in strengthening bioceramic scaffolds
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47 than any stress shielding that the load-bearing capacity of such a low-modulus polymeric
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49 material can produce [12].
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57 The mean compressive strength values with their corresponding errors bars are shown in
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59 Figure 11. The highest compressive strength was exhibited by scaffolds with dense struts (σ_c
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4 = 11 ± 4 MPa), while scaffolds with hollow struts were significantly weaker. As expected,
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6 the strength decreased with increasing internal channel diameter: $\sigma_c = 4 \pm 2$ MPa for $d_i/d =$
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8 0.45 and $\sigma_c = 3 \pm 1$ MPa for $d_i/d = 0.6$, although these differences were not found to be
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10 statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Nonetheless, the **strength** of hollow-struts TCP scaffolds
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12 was significantly improved (**more than doubled**) upon polymer infiltration ($\sigma_c = 9 \pm 3$ MPa
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14 and $\sigma_c = 9 \pm 2$ MPa for $d_i/d = 0.45$ and 0.6 , respectively). The observed strengthening (a
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16 factor of 2.5 and 2.7 for $d_i/d = 0.45$ and $d_i/d = 0.6$, respectively, **over hollow-strut scaffold**
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18 **values**) is due to the contribution of the two aforementioned mechanisms: defect healing and
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20 stress shielding. In any case, the strength of both hybrid structures is not statistically different
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22 ($p > 0.05$) to that of scaffolds with dense rods. This is a very positive finding, since the
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24 objective of this scaffold fabrication strategy is **to include the tougher polymeric core without**
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26 **jeopardizing the strength of the structure**. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that in terms of
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28 strength the new architecture is less favorable than that of scaffolds with dense rods coated
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30 with polymer, where a significant strength improvement can be achieved over the bare
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32 bioceramic structures [13,37]. In terms of functionality, all the samples show strengths
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34 comparable to that of natural bone, with room for additional improvement as the ceramic
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36 content of the ink could be increased or the separation between rods reduced in order to
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38 reduce the total porosity and, thus, increase the scaffold strength further.

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41 In order to better understand the role of parameters such as the modulus of the polymeric
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43 core and the diameter radius on the mechanical behavior of the hybrid scaffolds under
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45 compression, FEM simulations were used to evaluate the resulting changes in the stress field.
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48 Besides considering the dimensions of the scaffolds fabricated in this work, a batch of
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50 models with channel diameter ratios (d_i/d) ranging from 0.3 to 0.6, in steps of 0.05, was
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52 included in the analysis in order to broaden the design range. Figure 12 represents the
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4 evolution of the maximum tensile stress in a scaffold, which is always localized in the
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6 ceramic shell either at the internal channel or at the external surface close to the intersection
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8 between orthogonal rods (Figure 10), normalized by the externally applied stress, as a
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10 function of the elastic moduli ratio between the core and shell materials for scaffold models
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12 with the seven aforementioned diameter ratios (Figure 12a). Figure 12 also shows such
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14 evolution as a function of the diameter ratio for all core-shell stiffness ratios investigated
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16 (Figure 12b). In these plots, $E_{core}/E_{shell} = 1$ represents a dense-strut scaffold and $E_{core}/E_{shell} = 0$
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18 a scaffold with hollow struts.
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23 The results reported in these plots suggest that maximum stresses in the ceramic material are
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25 not significantly affected by the presence of the polymeric core until the moduli ratio
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27 becomes larger than 0.01, especially for scaffolds with the lower diameter ratios.
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31 Consequently, taking into account that the modulus ratio for PCL/TCP hybrid structures is
32
33 0.008, it is not surprising that even for the scaffolds with $d_i/d = 0.6$ the strengthening factor
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35 calculated for the experimental hybrid scaffolds over the hollow structures due to this stress
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37 reduction is less than 4%. Therefore, we can posit that the actual experimental strengthening
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39 factors, which are much larger, are achieved mainly thanks to the contribution of defect
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41 healing. This defect-healing strengthening mechanism has been reported to occur as well in
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43 TCP scaffolds coated with PCL with similar quantitative effects (strengthening factor of 2.2)
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45 [37]. Additionally, such defect healing mechanism reveals that mode II does not contribute
46
47 significantly to the fracture of the ceramic skeleton, since FEM simulations reveal that the
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49 Von Mises maximum stresses (Figure 13) are located at the external surface of the shells,
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51 right along the contact between struts where crack initiation should not be affected by the
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53 presence of the polymer in the channel.
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4 On the other hand, although the stress reduction (or stress-shielding) effect of PCL as a core
5 material is indeed very weak, the same would not be true for other polymers. Stiffer cores
6 would provide a more significant reduction of stresses, especially as the thickness of the
7 ceramic shell diminishes for a given strut diameter. As an example, the reduction of stresses
8 over hollow struts for hybrid scaffolds where the elastic modulus ratio was 0.1 (still feasible
9 with a polymeric core), will be of 30% for $d_i/d = 0.30$ and 60% for a diameter ratio of 0.60.
10 The results in Figure 12a indicate that the impact of the d_i variation should be stronger than
11 that reported in the experimental results for the mean compressive strength (Figure 11).
12 While experimental differences observed between the samples with the 2 different diameter
13 ratios are not statistically significantly ($p > 0.05$), both for hollow and hybrid scaffolds,
14 simulations predict clearly higher maximum stresses at the inner surfaces of the struts with
15 thinner walls. In more detail, for the ratios used experimentally, FEM results predict a
16 strength difference of 85% and 77% between them for hollow and hybrid scaffolds,
17 respectively (vs. the 15% or 4% observed in the experiments). This mismatch could be
18 attributed to geometrical differences in the real scaffolds at the location of the maxima.
19 Indeed, the DLP technique generates stair-step features in the interior of the shell, which
20 result in geometrical differences at the internal channel (Figure 6) that were not considered in
21 the FEM models and could explain the results. As it can be seen in those SEM images, for
22 $d_i/d = 0.6$ the higher radius of curvature results in a much flatter surface at the location of the
23 maxima which greatly reduces the concentration of stresses there, which can explain why the
24 hollow scaffolds with the larger internal diameter result much stronger than predicted by
25 FEM (0.29 vs. 0.17 times the strength of dense scaffolds). Another possible explanation
26 could be a Weibull size effect associated with the reduction in ceramic volume. Further
27 research would be needed in order to clarify which phenomenon is predominant. The results

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4 in Figure 12b indicate that the penalty in terms of compressive strength loss when increasing
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6 the size of the internal channel increases monotonically and, therefore, no fabrication
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8 guidelines other than trying to keep the channel diameter to the essential minimum to enable
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10 full polymer infiltration can be extracted from this data. In terms of the modulus of the core
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12 material, it is evident that the closer it is to that of the shell material, the better. The
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14 limitation is then that polymeric materials with the highest moduli tend to be brittle and, thus,
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16 would not provide the level of toughening and ductility exhibited by PCL in this study.
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18 Indeed, the toughening effect obtained after PCL infiltration into the strut's channels can be
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20 appreciated in Figure 14. In this plot, the mean values of the strain energy density
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22 corresponding to all types of specimens tested under compression, calculated as the area
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24 under stress-strain curves for strains up to 0.4, are represented with their corresponding
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26 deviations as error bars. Hybrid struts scaffolds possessed strain energy density values (2.1
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28 $\pm 0.4 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{m}^3$ and $2.6 \pm 0.6 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{m}^3$ for d_i/d of 0.45 and 0.60, respectively) that are one order of
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30 magnitude higher than those of the all-ceramic structures ($0.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{m}^3$ for dense and
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32 $0.60 d_i/d$ hybrid, and $0.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{m}^3$ for $0.45 d_i/d$ hollow struts scaffolds, respectively).
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34 Moreover, hybrid scaffolds exhibited values comparable to those of natural bone.
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36 Differences among the hybrid scaffolds were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), which
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38 seems to indicate that the toughness of the hybrid structures is not increased much by
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40 increasing the amount of polymer in the cores, provided it is already enough to hold the
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42 ceramic part together after it fails. Nonetheless, this conclusion must be confirmed in future
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44 studies, since the large dispersion of the gathered experimental data and the aforementioned
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46 geometrical differences existing between the scaffolds fabricated with different diameters
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48 may be masking existing differences if they are not large. It would also be interesting to look
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50 for any differences under other loading modes, such as bending, where the reduction in
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4 strength when moving from dense to hollow ceramic struts would be less important and thus
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6 might interfere less with the toughness results.
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9 The results of this work demonstrate that ceramic/polymer hybrid scaffolds with a core/shell
10 structure can be fabricated by DLP, and that the proposed architecture can provide, with an
11 appropriate design, the same level of strength as dense-strut structures but at the same time a
12 significantly improved toughness. Moreover, the level of strength and toughness achieved in
13 the hybrid DLP structures is similar to those obtained by DIW in previous works [22,23]
14 despite the much lower solid content in the starting suspension used for DLP. However, this
15 similarity is attributed to the abundant printing defects produced by the coaxial extrusion
16 process used in DIW, since the strength of dense DIW scaffolds in those studies was almost
17 twice that of DLP dense structures fabricated in this work. This only highlights the adequacy
18 of DLP for the fabrication of the hollow-strut ceramic preforms as it seems to avoid the
19 generation of the printing defects observed in coaxial DIW.
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36 Nonetheless, there is still room for improvement of the mechanical performance of scaffolds
37 designed with this novel architecture. If the conclusions of this study are confirmed, the
38 guideline for the design of such core/shell strut scaffolds would be to keep the polymeric
39 core size to a minimum in order to enhance the strength of the structure without jeopardizing
40 the toughness enhancement. Minimum size would be, thus, probably dictated by limitations
41 in the fabrication process, since reducing the channel size will make the infiltration process
42 more difficult. Further optimization of the design could also come from geometrical
43 adjustments on the shape and connections between channels and struts, seeking to minimize
44 stress concentrations and maximize the isotropy of the mechanical reinforcement provided
45 by the polymeric cores. For this purpose, DLP seems the proper technique to ensure the
46 correct fabrication of the scaffolds, given its high nominal resolution and design versatility.
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4 Mechanical optimization of the scaffolds may be realized also through further optimization
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6 of the ink composition and material selection. Maximization of solid loading in the starting
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8 slurry should be a priority, since this will minimize the generation of defects during
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10 debinding and sintering and reduce the final microporosity within the ceramic shells. All of
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12 this will lead to an enhancement of the bioceramic skeleton's strength. Strength could also be
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14 increased by reducing the distance separating the struts, although at the expense of reducing
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16 the porosity available for tissue ingrowth. Reducing the size of the struts could also
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18 potentially lead to an increase in the strength of the bioceramic structure due to Weibull's
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20 size effects, although the available reports on this issue are still contradictory [31,40,41]. The
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22 limited number of samples and the size of the scaffolds used in this study are not suitable for
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24 a detailed Weibull analysis of the fracture behavior: using larger specimens (with at least 7
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26 struts in each direction) and a greater number of samples would be required for any such
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28 comprehensive fracture study. Reinforcing the ceramic shell by using stronger materials or
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30 ceramic composites containing appropriate fillers, such as carbon nanotubes or graphene
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32 nanoplatelets [42–44], also offers interesting opportunities for further improvement.
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34 Regarding the polymeric core, stiffer but still ductile materials could prove more appropriate
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36 for this role than PCL, especially if biodegradability of the polymeric cores is not considered
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38 an essential feature. Using polymer composites for the strut cores could be another viable
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40 route for improving their stiffness, and this strategy could prove beneficial also in terms of
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42 biological response if, for instance, bioceramics or bioglass particles are used as fillers
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44 [45,46]. Nanocomposites, especially those reinforced with carbon-based materials such as
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46 graphene oxide or carbon nanotubes are also promising for this purpose [47]. Metallic
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48 materials could also be explored as an alternative to polymers for filling the channels,
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50 although their use will certainly pose a technological challenge as it will make the infiltration
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4 process much harder, and the expansion mismatch between the ceramic and the metal could
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6 lead to microcracking.
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9 Finally, topological optimization of the structure of the scaffolds enabling simultaneous
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11 maximization of strength and permeability would enable the fabrication, by AM, of
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13 improved bioceramic components for loadbearing and osteointegration applications.
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16 In any case, future work in this area will have to be carried out to help uncovering the full
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18 potential of this novel strategy for the fabrication of tough and strong bioactive scaffolds for
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20 bone regeneration and, of course, to validate their expected good biological performance
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22 both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.
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28 **4. Conclusions**

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30 Digital Light Processing (DLP) followed by suction-induced infiltration has been
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32 demonstrated to be a very suitable alternative for the production of hybrid ceramic/polymer
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34 scaffolds with core/shell struts. The fabricated TPC/PCL structures exhibited an order of
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36 magnitude enhancement in terms of the scaffold's toughness (strain energy density), without
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38 a significant reduction in the compressive strength, over dense-struts TCP scaffolds. The
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40 effect of the hollow core diameter on the amount of toughening appeared to be minor under
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42 this type of mechanical stresses, and thus, according to the FEM simulations, the size of the
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44 core should be minimized to avoid compromising the strength of the bioceramic skeleton.
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46 For the same reason, stiffness of the core material should be maximized, although this should
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48 not be done at the expense of completely sacrificing core ductility, since this would
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50 compromise the toughening effect. Further studies are still required to clarify existing
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52 unknowns in the optimization of this type of novel scaffold structures for biomedical
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54 applications.
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8

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53 **Figure Captions**

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4 Figure 1. Toughening strategies for bioceramic scaffolds by incorporating biopolymers: a)
5 conventional approaches by coating (left) or totally impregnating (right) the scaffold; and b)
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7 novel alternative by producing core/shell hybrid structures.
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14 Figure 2. Schematic diagrams of the structures used in this study. Scaffolds with (a) dense
15 and (b, c) hollow struts with d_i/d ratios of 0.45 and 0.60. Fabrication parameters (h , s , d , d_i)
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17 indicated in (c).
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24 Figure 3. Infiltration of the scaffold hollow struts by suction of molten PCL.
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28 Figure 4. Finite element model used to simulate the uniaxial compression of a coaxial hybrid
29 scaffold. The top surface was displaced perpendicularly by 200 μm , and the bottom surface
30 was fixed. The central cell with finer mesh ($\sim 25 \mu\text{m}$) is shown in the inset, and the rest of
31 the scaffold mesh was configured with larger elements (maximum 200 μm).
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41 Figure 5. SEM micrographs corresponding to lateral views of representative sintered
42 scaffolds with dense (a-c), hollow $d_i/d = 0.6$ (d-f) and hybrid $d_i/d = 0.45$ (g-i) struts.
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48 Figure 6. SEM cross-sectional micrographs of a hollow scaffold with $d_i/d = 0.6$. Higher
49 magnification images from the central micrographs are included on the lefts and right to
50 better show: (a) layer steps at the external surface and (c) absence of visible interlayers'
51 defects on a polished strut section.
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4 Figure 7. Measured dimensions for scaffolds with dense and hollow struts with either
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6 $d_i/d = 0.45$ and $d_i/d = 0.6$, before and after sintering, as indicated.
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11 Figure 8. Representative compressive stress-strain curves of the different types of scaffolds.
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16 Figure 9. Images captured *in-situ* during compression tests on each type of scaffold: (a)
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18 dense, (b) hollow $d_i/d = 0.45$, (c) hollow $d_i/d = 0.60$, (d) hybrid $d_i/d = 0.45$ and (e) hybrid
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20 $d_i/d = 0.60$, showing the damage generated in the struts (see arrows).
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26 Figure 10. Stress contours for the maximum principal tensile stress displayed on the
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28 representative central cell of (a) dense, (b) hollow and (c) hybrid scaffolds (with a d_i/d ratio
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30 of 0.45) after applying a compressive load.
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36 Figure 11. Compressive strength of the fabricated scaffolds. Data represents mean values
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38 with standard deviations as error bars. The shaded band represents typical values of human
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40 cancellous bone [1].
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45 Figure 12. Evolution of the maximum tensile stress in a scaffold (normalized by the
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47 externally applied stress) as a function of (a) the elastic moduli ratio for scaffold models with
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49 indicated diameter ratios and (b) the diameter ratio for scaffolds with indicated elastic moduli
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51 ratio.
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Figure 13. Von Mises stress contour plot on representative central cells of (a) dense, (b) hollow and (c) hybrid scaffolds (with a d_i/d ratio of 0.45), after applying a compressive load. Arrows indicate the locations of maximum stress.

Figure 14. Strain energy density up to a 0.4 strain evaluated from compression tests on different scaffolds, with standard deviations as error bars. The shaded band represents typical values for human bone [38,39].

a Dense

CENTRAL CELL

Figura6-FEM.tif

